

Interface Engineering for High-Performance Fully Printed Wide-Bandgap Perovskite Solar Cells with Carbon Electrodes

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Abstract

Fully printed wide-bandgap (WBG) perovskite solar cells are promising for semi-transparent Building-Integrated Photovoltaics, tandem top cells, and low-temperature indoor photovoltaics (PV), but their performance is hindered by high non-radiative recombination from interface defects and band alignment mismatch between charge transporting layers and the active halide layer, causing open circuit voltage (Voc) losses > 400 mV. To address this, we implement an interface-engineered design featuring bilayer electron transporting layers (ETLs), hole transporting layers (HTLs), and triethylamine hydrochloride (TEAHCl) modified SnO₂, which improves film uniformity, enhances conductivity, and suppresses interfacial recombination. This integrated approach achieves a low VOC deficit (< 200 mV) and high efficiencies of 16.51% on glass and 14.10% on flexible substrates.

In this work, TEAHCl incorporation was found to enhance SnO₂ film uniformity, delivering higher transmittance and conductivity. It also boosts perovskite crystallinity and absorption. Collectively, these improvements achieve efficiencies of 16.51% (glass) and 14.10% (flexible) with a

lower open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) deficit, highlighting strong practical potential in practical applications.

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